

Analysis of Service Aged Electromagnetic Protective Relays

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Abstract: For the investigation of failure behavior of electromechanical protective relays, a new evaluation method has been developed. This method is a qualitative method based on Failure Mode Effect and Criticality Analysis (FMECA) and the results of this investigation have been processed to:

- a list of failures and causes for a specific type of electromechanical protective relay,
- an evaluation of current and former maintenance policies.

1 INTRODUCTION

Protection systems in medium voltage grids consist for the largest part of protective relays of the electromechanical kind. The first series of this kind of protective relays were introduced in the late 40s. Later kinds (static and numerical) were introduced in the early 70s.

For years, these electromechanical protective relays have been serviced to an "as new" condition with a time based maintenance policy (preventive maintenance). This is no longer the case. The influence of no longer servicing to an "as new" condition and the ageing of these relays on the reliability of these relays has not been investigated.

2 ANALYSIS OF CURRENT PROTECTIVE RELAYING PRACTICES IN MEDIUM VOLTAGE GRIDS

Medium voltage networks in the Dutch grid are for the largest part represented by 10 kV level installations.

This study is mainly concentrated on 10 kV transportation/distribution networks commissioned by Dutch system operators. Figure 1 describes some typical installation setups on the 10kV level. Protective relaying in these setups consists of several types of protection systems. The combination of a protective relay and a circuit breaker forms the protection system. Each of these systems takes their share in protecting a system component. For example such components are:

- Transformer
- Bus bar
- Feeder/line

These components need to be protected against the following fault situations:

- Over current or over voltage:

Fig. 1: Typical medium voltage substation setups.

- Over currents occur during short circuit fault and over voltages occur after a lightning stroke.
- Duration (overload):
- In case of a line, cable or transformer carries a higher burden than the rated value.

In the Dutch medium voltage grids common types of protection are:

- over current protection,
- differential protection
- distance (zone) protection

The following tables give an indication of the magnitude of the Dutch sub transmission/distribution grids and presence of protective relays in these grids.

Table 1 is a summarized table of the information given

Tab. 1: Magnitude of the Dutch medium voltage network.

Medium voltage grid	
Voltage levels [kV] :	3, 6, 10, 12.5, 20 and 25
Number of substations:	103177
Grid length [km] :	91930

in [1]. A more detailed look into [1] shows that medium

Tab. 2: Presence of microprocessor based protective relays.

Type	Voltage $\leq$ 50 kV		
	Total	microprocessor based (numerical)	Percentage
Distance	3072	305	9.93%
Differential (zone)	2353	2	0.08%
Differential (transformer)	411	24	5.84%
Bus bar	35	0	0.00%
Over current	40132	981	2.44%
Total	46053	1362	2.96%

voltage grids are mainly represented by 10 kV level installations. The next table [2] shows gives an indication of the presence of protective relays in Dutch medium voltage grids. The information shows what type of protection systems are used in medium voltage grids. Table 2 also shows that the majority of protective relays are of older kinds of protective relays.

2.1 Reliability of protective relays

[3] Describes the reliability of the Dutch high/medium and low voltage grid. Most disturbances occur in medium voltage grids. Common causes for disturbances in the medium voltage grids are shown in figure 2. Disturbances caused by failing protective relays are not mentioned. Studies concerning the reliability of protective relays in the Dutch grids and especially the medium voltage grids are hardly available. Information about the performance of protection systems is only published in confidential company bound reports.

A failure of numerical relay can also be determined by the so-called "live contact". This feature makes it possible to assess the operational status of a protective relay by means of distance monitoring. Numerical protective relays have built in self-check functions, which regularly test the functionality of the protective relay. The live contact signals in case of a fail of a self-check. This feature is not available in electromechanical and (most) types of static relays. For this reason regular checks are required.

2.2 Efforts in maintaining the reliability of e.m. protective relays

The maintenance process needed to keep the protective relays operative has been a labor-intensive process for years. This is typically valid electromechanical protective relays. Electromechanical relays were checked in intervals of once per year. These checkups consisted of inspecting visually, testing, recalibration and if needed repair and refurbishing to an as new component. Since protective relays are mainly idle components in their operational life, regular checks can

only give confidence that a protective relay will operate

Fig. 2: Causes for disturbances in the medium voltage grid in 2002.

when it is supposed to. The later introduced static and numerical protective relays didn't have the need for such intensive maintenance activities. Manufacturers have recommended only visually inspecting and testing these relays since no or hardly any serviceable parts are present in these relays. Also the intervals of checkups were changed into longer intervals.

2.3 Changes and trends in maintenance activities in protective relaying

The past 10 to 15 years new insights in maintenance activities on protective relays and the recent liberalization of the Dutch energy market have forced some changes in the maintenance of protective relays. These changes affected the maintenance activities on electromechanical relays especially. One major change was the approach in the regular checkups. Electromechanical relays consist of some delicate components like moving coils, springs, contacts etc. A check-up in which these components are subjected to some invasive actions could damage these parts. Invasive actions are for example the burnishing of contacts, adjusting springs and adjustment of other mechanical parts. To carry out a more invasive inspection, a criterion has been set. Only in the case of not passing a functional test because of faulty or drifted settings, a more invasive inspection is allowed. This approach resulted in a gradual loss of skill of maintenance personnel in maintaining electromechanical relays.

Another factor of influence is that the manufacturers stopped the technical support on electromechanical protective relays in the mid 80s. Since then power companies are depending on their stored supplies of replacement parts. A common practice is the replacement by a protective relay from a spare feeder. The stretching of inspection intervals has become a common practice. The liberalization of the Dutch energy market is a factor of influence in this. The preventive maintenance approach is more and more shifting to a condition based approach.

3 TECHNIQUE FOR INVESTIGATING FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF E.M. PROTECTIVE RELAYS

3.1 Investigating causes of failures of e.m. protective relays

The way in which protective relays fail can in some cases tell a lot about what cause is accountable for this. Experienced engineers recognize the failure modes and know what effects these failure modes have on the components performance. A systematic way for documenting this knowledge is the Failure mode effect analysis (FMEA). The international standard IEC 812 describes the FMEA procedure. As a supplemental analysis to the FMEA, a criticality analysis (CA) can be carried out to focus the attention scope on to critical failure modes. FMEA or FMECA is an exhaustive procedure that results in an as complete as possible list of failure modes and causes for failures. Also part of the FMECA is composing a list of failure detection methods. The herein presented results of the FMECA procedure [5] are supplemented with an analysis of current maintenance practices.

3.2 Failure mode effect and criticality analysis

FMECA is part of a maintenance development program called the Reliability Centered Maintenance (RCM) or Maintenance Steering Group (MSG) method. This program consists of 6 steps which result in the definition of a new maintenance program. The RCM/MSG¹ method is described as follows:

1. Technical system decomposition:
which components form the technical systems?
2. Recognize significant components:
on what components should attention be focused?
3. Failure mode analysis:
investigate failure behavior of components
4. Select maintenance policy:
evaluate maintenance necessities
5. Specify maintenance task:
describe process of maintenance activities
6. Define maintenance program:
organize maintenance activities

The goal of the FMECA procedure here is to find answers for the following questions:

- What is a likely way in which a part fails?
- What mechanisms are responsible for these failure modes?
- What could the effects be if the failures did occur?
- Is the failure in the safe or unsafe direction?
- How is a failure detected?
- What inherent provisions are provided in the design to compensate for the failure?

These questions are fitted into a structured approach defined by the IEC 812 standard. The IEC812 standard

Fig. 3: FMECA spreadsheet overview

states that information necessary for carrying out a FMECA should cover (if possible) three categories. These categories are:

1. System structure
2. System initiation, operation, control and maintenance
3. System environment

Figure 3 shows an overview of how the FMECA is organized. This forms the basis for the developed FMECA spreadsheet program treated in the next paragraphs

3.3 Functional description of an electromechanical protective relay setup

An e.m. protective relay can be described by four processes. These processes are:

- Detection
- Actuation
- Tripping
- Time setting & Calibration

The detection and tripping processes represent the input- and output circuits. The actuation part describes the operating principle. Two common operating principles are:

- Armature attracted
- Induction disk

The Time setting & Calibration process describes the way in which the operation of the three other processes is influenced. An electromechanical protective relay can be described by the functional block diagram, see figure

4. The four process description forms also the basis for the subsystem decomposition of an electromechanical protective relay.

Fig. 4: Functional block diagram.

- Subsystem.
- System element (component).
- Function.
- Failure mode.
- Failure cause
- Local effect of failure
- End effect of failure
- Detection provisions
- Preventive actions

The described subjects cover most basic FMECA questions. Figure 5 shows how these subjects are implemented in an FMECA sheet.

Induction disc relay GE IFC ser Failure mode effects and criticality analysis													
Subsystem	System element	Function	Failure mode	Failure causes	Failure effect		Failure detection	Preventive actions	Detection D	Occurrence O	Severity S	RPN	
					Local effect	End effect							
Detection	U-magnet	create emf in coils											
	19	Coil (upper pole)	create/induce emf in disc	short circuit	aged insulation	-	No trip	measurement of coil resistance	none	2	3	5	30
	20	Coil (upper pole)		short circuit	dirt/dust	-	No trip	measurement of coil resistance	none	2	3	5	30
	21	Coil (upper pole)		loose	rough handling	-	No trip	measurement of coil resistance	handle with care	2	4	4	32
	22	Coil (upper pole)		broken	rough handling	-	No trip	measurement of coil resistance	handle with care	2	4	5	40
	23	Taps	set magnitude of detection current	no detection	wrongly set	-	No trip	functional test	compare with tapsetting main unit	3	2	5	30
	24	Taps		loose	disconnected	-	No trip	Check connections	connections after disconnection	2	2	5	20
	25	Coil (lower pole)	create/induce emf in disc	short circuit	aged insulation	-	No trip	measurement of coil resistance	none	2	3	5	30
	26	Coil (lower pole)		short circuit	dirt/dust	-	No trip	measurement of coil resistance	none	2	3	5	30
	27	Coil (lower pole)		loose	rough handling	-	No trip	measurement of coil resistance	handle with care	2	3	5	30
28	Coil (lower pole)		broken	rough handling	-	No trip	measurement of coil resistance	handle with care	2	3	5	30	
Actuation	Drag magnet	drag disc											
	29	Locking nut	adjust drag on disk	loose	not tightened in last adjustment	-	Conditional: no effect if	Setting / calibration	tighten nut	3	1	5	15
	30	Locking nut		stuck	corrosion	no longer adjustable	Conditional: no effect if adjusted ok	Setting / calibration	none	3	1	1	3
	31	Magnet	cause drag on disk	decreased magnetic strength	magnetic material degradation	possible less drag	Early trip	drag (no adjustment tolerance)	none	5	1	3	15
	32	Magnet		damaged / broken	rough handling	possible less drag	Early trip	inspection	handle with care	3	2	3	18

Fig. 5: FMECA sheet.

3.4 Subsystem approach

Normally, a FMECA is conducted only on the part level. Here, this still is done with the difference that all parts are assigned to subsystems. These subsystems are related to the functional description. The subsystem approach brings the following advantages:

- Local effects of part failures can be described more detailed.
- Influence of local effect on the end effect can be described.
- The effectiveness of failure detection methods can be evaluated.

3.5 Constructing a FMECA sheet

The basic input of a FMECA sheet is the textual description of the following:

4 EVALUATION OF FAILURE BEHAVIOR OF AN ELECTROMECHANICAL OVER CURRENT PROTECTIVE RELAY

4.1 Analyzed electromechanical protective relay setup

The described FMECA procedure is conducted on an e.m. over current protective relay. The analyzed relay setup is a common induction disk relay as manufactured by ABB and GE. This unit has both operating principles. The main unit is an induction disk type. The relay setup has a backup unit which has the armature attracted operating principle.

Fig. 6: Subsystem setup of an induction disk unit

Fig. 7: Subsystem setup of an armature attracted unit.

4.2 Decomposition of subsystems

The subsystem setup of the induction disk unit can be described by using the functional block diagram. This results in the figure 6. A subsystem decomposition of an armature attracted unit is described in figure 7. The armature attracted unit is a simpler setup. An induction disk unit consists of more components. A further decomposition of the subsystems results in a total overview of subsystems and their associated components. The result of this decomposition results in the following overviews, see figures 8-9.

4.3 Causes, failure modes and effects

The identification of failure modes, causes and their effects resulted in a list of 54 events in 21 components. These events are summarized into 10 failure modes with 8 general causes and 4 end effects. The following figure shows the relationships between causes, failure modes

Fig. 8: Subsystem overviews:

- a) "time setting and calibration" and its related components
- b) "Detection" and its related components

Fig. 9: Subsystem overviews:

- a) "Actuation" and its related components
- b) "Tripping" and its related components

Fig. 10: Causes for failures, failure modes and failure effects

and end effects. The failure effects explain in which way a failure mode affects the operation of a protective relay. The function of a protective relay is to energize the trip circuit of a circuit breaker. This will cause the circuit breaker to isolate the faulted line. The failure effects as described in fig 10 are defined in table 3. These overviews form the basis on which FMECA procedure is carried out.

Tab. 3: Description of failure effects

Failure effect	Description
No trip	System does not generate a trip signal. Circuit breaker does not act in fault situation.
Delayed trip	System generates a trip signal but not within required time constraint. Circuit breaker acts on trip signal but is stressed longer.
Early trip	System generates a trip signal earlier than the required time constraint. Circuit breaker acts on trip signal.
Trip without seal in	System generates a trip signal but does not energize circuit breaker trip circuit sufficiently. Circuit breaker does not act in fault situation.

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breaker to isolate the faulted line. The failure effects as described in fig 10 are defined in table 3.

These four failure effects can be assigned to general categories, which are useful when defining a performance indicator for protective relays. These categories are:

- Missing operation [No trip, No seal in]
- Unwanted operation [Delayed trip, Early trip]

5 CONCLUSIONS

Based on this study the following can be concluded:

1. The failure behavior of electromechanical protective relays can be evaluated with the use the FMECA method.
2. Electromagnetic protective relays are ageing since they are no longer serviced to an "As new" condition.
3. The current set of applied failure detection methods is not sufficient for finding mechanical component failures.
4. The servicing process currently is focused on the verification of the functionality of the protective relay.

6 REFERENCES

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